

Synthesis of Some 2-Phenoxyethylbenzimidazoles

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A large number of benzimidazole derivatives have been reported to possess trypano-somicidal and spirocheticidal¹ action and are active against diseases caused by protozoa. 2-Alkoxyethylbenzimidazoles possess antipyretic activity². Some other substituents, when introduced in position 2, impart antihistaminic³ and antimalarial⁴⁻⁵ activity, and also their utility as local anaesthetics⁶. In general, compounds having substituents in position 2 have been found to be very much pharmacologically active. The data on 2-phenoxyethyl derivatives are, however, lacking in the literature. It is considered therefore worthwhile to synthesise 2-phenoxyethylbenzimidazoles involving variations in the phenoxy nucleus for testing purposes.

2-Phenoxyethylbenzimidazoles (Table I) have been obtained by condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with 2-chloro-(I), 4-chloro-(II), 2-bromo-(III), 4-bromo-(IV), 2,4-dichloro-(V), 4-nitro-(VI), 2-methyl- (VII), 3-methyl-(VIII), 4-methyl-(IX), 2,4-dimethyl-(X), 2,5-dimethyl-(XI), 2,6-dimethyl-(XII), 3,5-dimethyl-(XIII), and 4-chloro-5-methyl-(XIV) phenoxyacetic acids and 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine with (I), (II), (VII) (IX), (XI), and (XIV) in presence of hydrochloric acid (Method I)⁷. Identical products were obtained when 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole was condensed with the corresponding phenols in alkaline medium (Method II). Phenoxyacetic acids have been prepared by the method of Coelsch⁸.

Method I.—A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.02*M*), appropriate phenoxyacetic acid (0.03*M*), and 4*N*-HCl (20 ml) was refluxed for about 1hr. The product was then cooled and kept overnight. The benzimidazole derivative was precipitated by adding sodium carbonate solution and crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate.

1. Walter *et al.* (Winthrop Chemical Co.), U. S. P. 2242581; *Chem. Abs.*, 1941, 35, 5648.
2. Bayer & Co., B.P. 243766; *Chem. Abs.*, 1927, 21, 158.
3. Wright, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2035.
4. Busford *et al.* (Imperial Chemical Industries Ltd.), B.P. 593499; *Chem. Abs.* 1948, 42, 2291.
5. Chatterjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2965.
6. Pützer and Schönhöfer (I.G. Farbenindustrie, A.G.), D. R. P. 556327; *Chem. Abs.*, 1932, 26, 4062.
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8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53, 304.

TABLE I

S.No.	Phenoxyacetic acid used.	Benzimidazole obtained.	*M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.	
A. Diamine used: <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine (R = H).							
1	2-Chloro-	2-(2'-chloro-)-X	190°	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.72	10.83
2	4-Chloro-	2-(4'-chloro-)-X	174°	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.67	10.83
3	2-Bromo-	2-(2'-bromo-)-X	184°	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Br	9.11	9.24
4	4-Bromo-	2-(4'-bromo-)-X	201°	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Br	9.15	9.24
5	2,4-Dichloro-	2-(2', 4'-dichloro-)-X	175°	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂	9.23	9.56
6	4-Nitro-	2-(4'-nitro-)-X	202°	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃	15.27	15.61
7	2-Methyl-	2-(2'-methyl-)-X	182°	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₂	11.49	11.76
8	3-Methyl-	2-(3'-methyl-)-X	120°	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₂	11.36	11.76
9	4-Methyl-	2-(4'-methyl-)-X	148°	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₂	11.51	11.76
10	2,4-Dimethyl-	2-(2',4'-dimethyl-)-X	100°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.65	11.11
11	2,5-Dimethyl-	2-(2',5'-dimethyl-)-X	194°	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.82	11.11
12	2,6-Dimethyl-	2-(2',6'-dimethyl-)-X	174°	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.77	11.11
13	3,5-Dimethyl-	2-(3',5'-dimethyl-)-X	222°	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.69	11.11
14	4-Chloro-5-methyl-	2-(4'-chloro-5'-methyl-)-X	155°	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	10.05	10.29
B. Diamine used : 4 methyl- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine (R = Me).							
1	2-Chloro-	2-(2'-chloro-)-Y	122°	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	10.10	10.28
2	4-Chloro-	2-(4'-chloro-)-Y	146°	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	10.08	10.28
3	2-Methyl-	2-(2'-methyl-)-Y	130°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.82	11.11
4	4-Methyl-	2-(4'-methyl-)-Y	144°	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.68	11.11
5	2,5-Dimethyl-	2-(2',5'-dimethyl-)-Y	187°	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ON ₂	10.32	10.52
6	4-Chloro-5-methyl-	2-(4'-chloro-5' methyl-)-Y	170°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₂ Cl	9.37	9.77

X = Phoxymethylbenzimidazole,

Y = Phoxymethyl-5-methylbenzimidazole.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

Method II.—A mixture of 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole (0.02M) and phenol (0.03M), dissolved in excess of ethanolic alkali, was refluxed for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product was cooled, precipitated by addition of water, and crystallised as above.

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